

TECHNOLOGY OF MAKING FLOUR FROM LOCAL WHEAT GRAINS

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Annotation: Production technology of jaidari flour from wheat and rye grains. Production technology of single-grade rye flour. Production technology of two types of rye flour. Flour production technology in a complex way without enrichment of intermediate products. Flour production technology for bread products of three types of wheat grain 75-78%.

Keywords: Fraction, technological processes, BVU equipment, intermediate product, single-grade flour, two-grade flour, three-grade flour.

Introduction: Flour and cereal products are the main food products consumed. If 2.0-2.5 million tons of wheat grains are used for bread and bakery products for public consumption from grain-related plants grown in our republic in recent years, and from the rest, a variety of mixed feed products for livestock, poultry and other industries are supplied. There are more than 50 flour mills, about 15 flour mills and more than 35 mixed fodder producing enterprises and more than 35 mixed fodder producing enterprises in the republic. In this field, it is possible to cite as an example the highly productive Bühler company in Switzerland, the enterprises in Germany, the Czech Republic, Slovakia, Italy, and Turkey equipped with technological equipment with new technological regulations, control and management devices for the automation of technological processes.

Currently, the mills built in cooperation with German and Turkish companies in Alpomish, Kashkadarya, Shahrikesh, and Chinoz district of Tashkent region produce high-quality flour products. The above-mentioned enterprises make up a large part of the food industry, and the products they produce contain chemicals necessary for the human body. Human food ration always consists of more than six hundred substances, its importance. There is no food plant other than grain that has this property. The basics of the technology of production of flour and mixed fodder are mainly taught after the following subjects: commodity science of grain and grain products, elevator and warehouse management, grain biochemistry, microbiology, theoretical mechanics, etc.

A general description of the flour milling technology. Flour is a cereal product, it is ground. If the flour is made only from the inner parts of the grain (endosperm), it is called graded flour. The flour obtained by grinding grain together with husks and husks is called jaidari (ordinary) flour. Wheat, rye and triticale grains are mainly used for making flour. According to the requirements of the consumers, flour is also made from oat, buckwheat, corn and barley grains. Different types of flour differ in their chemical composition. As a result of various processes, the kernel of cereal grains is separated from the upper flower and seed shells.

Only the husk is separated from the buckwheat grain and cereal is prepared. Buckwheat, rice, millet, oat, barley, corn, wheat, peas, and white corn are used to prepare groats. Flour products made from wheat grains are in the main place in consumption due to their richness

in protein and other chemical elements. Cereal products belong to the group of semi-finished products, from which meals can be prepared with less time. Cereal made from sorghum is very useful for the human body and health. It is rich in protein and vitamins. In this industry, oat products are prepared for breakfast with milk. "Karshi-Dunyo-M" enterprise produces a special cereal product for children from wheat grains. It differs from other cereals due to its richness in various vitamins, fat and other macro and micro elements. All flour production processes are based on scientifically based principles, and they are described in "Rule". As a result of the introduction of new technologies and techniques into the technological processes of flour and semolina production, the existing technological processes are being improved.

As mentioned above, 96% of jaidari wheat flour and 87% of first-grade rye flour are obtained in simple flour production technological processes. In the production of Jaidari wheat flour and rye grain flour, a three-group system of successive grinding of grains is used. Batches are sent from one system to another, separated from the intermediate products being crushed. In the technological processes of flour milling, milled grain and intermediate semi-finished products are processed in parallel in a row. Intermediate and semi-finished products are mainly high-quality cereals. In order to improve the quality of these products, they are processed in parallel with the main product.

This technological process can be used to obtain 87% rye flour and jaidari flour. Production technology of jaidari flour from wheat and rye grains. Jaidari flour production uses 3-4 grinding equipment, intermediate products sorting machines and one or two grinding equipment and finished products control machines.

Figure 56. Technological drawing of rye flour production.

In the drawing, 4 systems are used for grinding, and the systems are used for controlling flour. The lower sieve shafts of the IV system (4-075) are sent to the Vimol process to extract bran from BVU. Flour and bran are obtained from the output of the A1-BVU equipment.

The first grade 87% rye flour production technology is related to the production plan of rye flour, which is ground in series and parallel grain systems. In the production of flour from rye grain, the scheme given above is the most widely used scheme.

As a rule, the design for the production of "obdir" flour consists of four-five grinding and one flour weighing system. Technology of flour production in a complex way without enrichment of intermediate products. This type of flour production includes: second-grade 87% rye flour, first-grade 63% rye flour, and first-grade 85% wheat flour production methods.

In this way, the reason for dividing flour production into one group is that intermediate products are not enriched in them. Production technology for bread products of three types of wheat grain 75-78%, this technological drawing is widely used in the field. Based on this technological drawing, flour with 75-78% starch content is produced in various variants.

In practice, based on the demand of the population, three types of baking flour production technological processes have been established.

This version of Figure 65 below shows five crushing, five screening and two additional crushing systems. In the grinding system, II, III and IV processes are divided into large and small systems, and they grind the wood coming from the previous grinding system.

First quality products are obtained from the first three grinding systems, and second quality products are obtained in IV system, V grinding and BVU equipment are included in additional grinding systems.

Figure 65. Layout diagram of grinding and sorting systems in the production of three types of flour from wheat grain.

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